

Relation between Hydration and Stability of Sols and the Bivalent Nature of Fluoride Ion.

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Colloids have been divided into two classes *viz.*, lyophile and lyophobe. There are, however, no definite criteria of distinguishing one class of the sol from the other. For example, gelatin, albumin, gum arabic, soap and saponin show much greater viscosity and markedly less surface tension than the dispersing medium, water. These sols are also highly stable towards electrolytes and readily form stiff jelly even in the diluted condition. These substances are typically lyophilic in nature and are considered to be highly solvated, but no direct experiments proving their great amount of hydration have yet been done. Though starch and agar agar have been classified as lyophile colloids they do not show marked decrease of surface tension but their other properties are the same as those of the first group of lyophile colloids.

We (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 152, 399 ; 1927, 164, 63) have shown that sols of vanadium pentoxide and ceric hydroxide are more viscous than water and form stiff jellies even when dilute but they are unstable and readily coagulated by univalent electrolytes and their surface tension seems to be very slightly less than that of water. Hence it will be clear that it is difficult to state definitely the points of difference between lyophile and lyophobe colloids.

In communications (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 162, 237 ; 168, 209 ; *Kolloid. Zeit.*, 1927, 42, 120) from these laboratories we have shown that colloids can be divided into two classes according to their behaviour on ageing. In one class of sols the viscosity decreases and the surface tension and conductivity increase on ageing and this class appears to be less hydrated. The other class of sol becomes more viscous and less conducting and more hydrated on ageing. These latter class of sols are lyophilic in nature. If we classify the sols from the above criteria, hydroxides of iron, aluminium, chromium, tin, thorium, ceric (prepared in the hot), ferrocyanides of

iron and copper and arsenious sulphide and crystal violet show lyophobic behaviour, whilst vanadium pentoxide, ceric hydroxide (prepared in the cold) and gelatin have been found to possess lyophilic character.

It has been believed that there is a close relationship between the degree of hydration of a sol and its stability towards electrolytes. In a recent paper (*Kolloid. Zeit.*, 1928, **44**, 149) we have shown that the amount of electrolytes of different valencies required to coagulate the sols of ceric hydroxide, thorium hydroxide, ferric hydroxide and stannic hydroxide prepared in the cold and hot conditions are not very different from each other. The amount of hydration, however, is much greater with sols prepared in the cold than in the hot condition as is evident from their greater viscosities and the more gelatinous nature of the precipitates obtained with sols prepared in the cold than those in the hot. Thus we have obtained stable jellies with ceric hydroxide sol prepared in the cold whilst the sol prepared in the hot only forms a flocculent precipitate on coagulation. Similarly, we have observed that the precipitate from ferric hydroxide sol prepared in the hot is more granular than the precipitate obtained from the sol prepared in the cold. Hence it appears that greater hydration is not always associated with greater stability towards electrolytes.

In the same paper we have shown that the high coagulating power of fluoride ions observed with several positively charged sols is certainly due to their bivalent nature ($F_2^{''}$) and not due to their greater degree of hydration than other halogen ions as has been assumed by Freundlich and Aschenbrenner (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1927, **41**, 37).

In this paper we have studied the coagulation of the hydroxides of zirconium, chromium and aluminium in order to strengthen our foregoing conclusions.

(1) *Zirconium hydroxide sol.*—This sol was prepared by (a) dialysing a zirconium nitrate solution and (b) boiling a zirconium nitrate solution and then dialysing the boiled solution. The first sol was the one prepared in the cold and the second sol was the one prepared in the hot. Both the sols form firm transparent jellies when coagulated by KCl, whilst only broken gelatinous precipitates are obtained when coagulated by bivalent or polyvalent anions. The following tables contain the results when zirconium hydroxide sol prepared in the cold and hot conditions are coagulated by different electrolytes.

TABLE I.

Coagulation of zirconium hydroxide sol prepared in the cold.

Concentration of the sol = 9.42 gms. ZrO_2 per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time = 2 c.c. Volume = 4 c.c.

Time = 1/2 hour.

Electrolytes.	Concentration.	Amount to gelatinise in c.c.	Precipitation value.
KCl	N/2	0.70	0.0875
KBr	N/2	0.80	0.1000
KI	N/2	0.90	0.1125
K_2SO_4	N/50	1.55	0.0078
K_2F_6	N/37.8	1.50	0.0106
$K_2C_2O_4$	N/50	1.90	0.0095
Sodium tartrate	N/50	2.2	0.0110
$K_4Fe(CN)_6$	N/500	1.25	0.0006

TABLE II.

Coagulation of zirconium hydroxide sol prepared in the hot.

Concentration of the sol = 9.56 gms. ZrO_2 per litre.

Sol A = 2 c.c. of the sol made up to 4 c.c. Time = 1 hour.

Precipitation value.

Electrolyte.	Sol A.	Sol A/2.
KCl N/4	0.0437	0.0437
KBr N/4	0.0531	0.0500
KI N/4	0.0812	0.0812
K_2SO_4 N/50	0.0070	0.0050
K_2F_6 N/37.8	0.0100	0.0070
$K_2C_2O_4$ N/50	0.0090	0.0065
Sodium tartrate N/50	0.0095	0.0080
$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ N/500	0.0006	0.0004

Tables I and II show that the precipitation values of different

anions are in the following increasing order for both the sols:—
ferrocyanide > sulphate > oxalate > tartrate > fluoride > chloride
> bromide > iodide.

It will be also seen that zirconium hydroxide sol behaves normally towards dilution when coagulated by electrolytes. In the following tables the results are recorded when the sol prepared in the hot is coagulated with mixtures of KCl and K_2SO_4 .

TABLE III.

Amount of sol taken each time = 2 c.c.
Volume = 4 c.c. Time = 1/2 hour.

Amount of KCl added in c.c. N/4	Amount of K_2SO_4 required to coagulate in c.c. N/50.		
	Added.	Calculated.	Difference.
0.7	—	—	—
0	1.40	—	—
0.1	1.20	1.20	0
0.2	1.05	1.00	+0.05
0.3	0.80	0.80	0
0.4	0.62	0.60	+0.02

The above table shows that additive amounts of KCl and K_2SO_4 are required to coagulate the sol.

(2) *Chromium hydroxide sol.*—This sol was prepared in the cold by adding ammonium carbonate solution to a chromium chloride solution at the room temperature (25°) till a slight precipitate obtained just dissolved on shaking. The deep green coloured sol was left for dialysis till it was free from electrolytes. A portion of the sol was next boiled for more than 20 minutes and thus the sol was prepared in the hot condition. In the following tables the results are given when the sols prepared in the cold as well as in the hot are coagulated by bivalent anions, as both the sols could not be coagulated by even 2N KCl, 2N KBr etc.

TABLE IV.

*Coagulation of chromium hydroxide prepared in the cold.*Concentration of the sol=1.725 gm. Cr_2O_3 per litre.

Amount taken each time=2 c.c.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour.

Electrolyte.	Concentration.	Amount to coagulate in c.c.	Precipitation value.
K_2F_2	N/15.12	1.00	0.0132
K_2SO_4	N/50	0.80	0.0032
$\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	N/50	0.95	0.0038
Sodium tartrate	N/50	0.80	0.0032

The precipitation values are in the following increasing order :—
sulphate > tartrate > oxalate > fluoride.

TABLE V.

*Coagulation of boiled chromium hydroxide sol.*Concentration of the sol=1.725 gm. Cr_2O_3 per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time=2 c.c.

Volume=5 c.c. Time=1 hour.

Electrolyte.	Concentration.	Amount to coagulate in c.c.	Precipitation value.
K_2F_2	N/15.12	0.80	0.0105
K_2SO_4	N/50	0.70	0.0028
$\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	N/50	0.80	0.0032
Sodium tartrate	N/50	0.75	0.0030

The precipitation values are in the following increasing order :—
sulphate > tartrate > oxalate > fluoride.

(3) *Aluminium hydroxide sol.*

The sol was prepared by adding an excess of CH_3COONa to a solution of aluminium nitrate and then dialysing the mixture till it was free from electrolytes. The sol thus prepared in the cold was next boiled in order to obtain the sol in the hot condition. Like chromium hydroxide sols both the sols of aluminium hydroxide

could not be coagulated by concentrated solutions of KCl, KBr and KI. The following are the results obtained when the sols of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ are coagulated by bivalent anions.

TABLE VI.

Coagulation of aluminium hydroxide sol prepared in the cold.

Concentration of the sol = 1.32 gms. Al_2O_3 per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time = 2 c.c.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour.

Electrolyte.	Concentration.	Amount to coagulate in c.c.	Precipitation value.
K_2F_6	N/37.8	1.65	0.0085
K_2SO_4	N/50	0.85	0.0035
$\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	N/50	1.00	0.0040
Sodium tartrate	N/50	0.90	0.0038

The precipitation values are in the following increasing order:—
sulphate > tartrate > oxalate > fluoride.

TABLE VII.

Coagulation of boiled sol of aluminium hydroxide,

Concentration of the sol = 1.32 gm. Al_2O_3 per litre.

Amount of sol taken each time = 2 c.c.

Volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour.

Electrolyte.	Concentration.	Amount to coagulate in c.c.	Precipitation value.
K_2F_6	N/37.8	1.50	0.0079
K_2SO_4	N/50	0.75	0.0030
$\text{K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	N/50	0.90	0.0036
Sodium tartrate	N/50	0.80	0.0032

The precipitation values are in the following increasing order:—
sulphate > tartrate > oxalate > fluoride.

The experimental results show that the amounts of electrolytes necessary for coagulating the sols prepared in the hot and cold conditions are very slightly different. In all cases the amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate a sol obtained in the hot condition is

slightly smaller than those required for the sols prepared in the cold. This is possibly due to the fact that the stabilising electrolytes adsorbed by the sols are smaller in the cases of those prepared in the hot than those obtained in the cold. Hence these results support the conclusion that the stability of a sol is not associated with its amount of hydration.

It will be interesting to note that zirconium hydroxide prepared in the hot and cold conditions form stable jellies. Similarly, we have shown that silicic acid sols prepared at the ordinary and the boiling temperatures also form jellies. Ceric hydroxide sol on the other hand forms jellies only from the sols prepared in the cold. From our measurements (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **168**, 209) of viscosity, of silicic acid we find that the viscosities of the two sols are not very different. The viscosity of the ceric hydroxide sol prepared in the hot is, however, much smaller than that of the sol obtained in the cold. We have now measured the viscosities of the two sols of zirconium hydroxide and find that it is 0.00968 for the sol prepared in the cold containing 7.54 gms. of ZrO_2 per litre and 0.01068 for the sol prepared in the hot containing 8.5 gms. of ZrO_2 per litre at 30° , whilst that of water at the same temperature is 0.00803. Hence the viscosities of the sols prepared in two different conditions are not different and thus we obtain jellies in both the cases very readily. Moreover the following results (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1846; *Kolloid. Zeit.*, 1927, **42** 124) show that as compared to the hydroxides of aluminium, iron and chromium the viscosity, of zirconium hydroxide is appreciably greater.

TABLE VIII.

Temperature 30°.

Sol.	Concentration gms. per litre.	Viscosity.
Water	—	0.00803
Zr(OH) ₂	7.54 gm. ZrO ₂	0.00968
Fe(OH) ₃	9.14 gm. Fe ₂ O ₃	0.00886
Al(OH) ₃	15.6 gm. Al ₂ O ₃	0.00880
Cr(OH) ₃	8.13 gm. Cr ₂ O ₃	0.01079 at 28.1°
Water	—	0.00837 ..

This greater viscosity of $Zr(OH)_4$ sol is associated with its property of forming jellies readily.

Viscosities of $Ce(OH)_4$ and V_2O_5 sols are much greater than those of hydroxides of iron, aluminium and chromium. We have shown that $Ce(OH)_4$ prepared in the cold and V_2O_5 sols from jellies more readily than the above hydroxides. Moreover, in a foregoing paper we (*Kolloid. Zeit.*, 1927, 42, 124) have shown that for the same concentration, $Fe(OH)_3$ sol is more viscous than As_2S_3 sol and it is well known that As_2S_3 sol cannot form a jelly. Hence the foregoing results conclusively prove that the tendency to form a jelly and high viscosity are always associated with a greater degree of solvation.

The foregoing results show that the coagulating power of fluoride ion towards the positively charged hydroxide sols is of the same order as that of the bivalent ions like sulphate, oxalate and tartrate. In the cases of $Al(OH)_3$ and $Cr(OH)_3$ the coagulating power of fluoride ion is slightly less than those of sulphate, oxalate and tartrate. This is possibly due to the fact that a part of K_2F_6 is removed by the formation of complex fluorides. It is well known that stable complex salts of the type M_3AlF_6 , M_3CrF_6 , etc., are formed by the action of M_2F_6 on hydroxides or salts of aluminium and chromium. It seems certain that the fluoride ion exists in the bivalent condition in aqueous solutions and therefore exerts a coagulating effect of the same order as the bivalent ions, sulphate, oxalate and tartrate.

Summary.

(1) Experimental results on the coagulation of zirconium hydroxide sols prepared in the cold and hot conditions by chloride, bromide and iodide ions show that the precipitation values of these ions are greater in the case of the sol prepared in the cold than in the hot. The precipitation values of ferrocyanide, sulphate, oxalate, tartrate and fluoride ions are slightly greater in the case of zirconium hydroxide prepared in the cold than in the hot.

(2) Zirconium hydroxide sol requires smaller quantities of electrolytes in the diluted condition than in the concentrated and shows additive relationship when coagulated by a mixture of electrolytes.

(3) The precipitation values of sulphate, tartrate, oxalate, and fluoride ions are slightly greater in the cases of sols of chromium and

aluminium hydroxides prepared in the cold than those prepared in the hot condition.

(4) It seems that the stabilising electrolytes adsorbed by the sols are smaller in the case of those prepared in the hot than those obtained in the cold.

(5) The stability of a sol appears not to be associated with its amount of hydration.

(6) Zirconium hydroxides, prepared in the hot and cold conditions, have practically the same viscosity and form stiff jelly in both the cases. Viscosities of zirconium hydroxide, vanadium pentoxide, and ceric hydroxide are greater than those of ferric, chromium, and aluminium hydroxides. Jellies are formed more readily with the first group of hydroxides than with the second.

(7) Tendency to form a jelly and high viscosity are associated with higher degree of solvation of the sol and are the most important criteria of lyophile colloids.

(8) Fluoride ions exist in the bivalent condition (F_2^{2-}) in aqueous solution and exerts a coagulating effect of the same order as the bivalent ions, sulphate, oxalate, and tartrate.

